

AI4

WP4 Updated implementation plan and progress report

Deliverable ID	D4.3 - WP4 Updated implementation plan and progress report
Work Package Reference	WP4
Issue	1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	31/08/2024
Submission Date	31/08/2024
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Lead Partner	INFN
Contributors	CSIC, KIT, IISAS, UPV, PREDICTIA, LIP, PSNC, MMIS, WODR
Grant Agreement No	101058593
Call ID	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	10.5281/zenodo.11485120
Website	https://ai4eosc.eu/

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services),

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services),

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
A. Costantini (INFN) J. Sáinz-Pardo (CSIC) V. Kozlov (KIT) S. Dlugolinsky (IISAS) C. Alarcón (UPV) G. Moltó (UPV)	M. Obregón Ruiz (CSIC) G. Donvito (INFN) I. Heredia (CSIC) M. Plociennik (PSNC)	Project Management Board

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	08/07/2024	Table of Content	A. Costantini (INFN)
0.2	13/07/2024	Initial version of the complete deliverable	A. Costantini (INFN) J. Sáinz-Pardo (CSIC) V. Kozlov (KIT) S. Dlugolinsky (IISAS) C. Alarcón (UPV) G. Moltó (UPV)
0.3	31/07/2024	WP4 internal review	M. Obregón Ruiz (CSIC) G. Donvito (INFN)
0.4	10/08/2024	First external review	I. Heredia (CSIC) M. Plociennik (PSNC)
1.0	26/08/2024	Final review and acceptance	Á. López (CSIC)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of tables	4
List of figures	4
Executive summary	5
1. - Introduction	5
2. - Progress report	6
2.1 - Architecture updates	6
2.2 - Roadmap evaluation update	7
3. - AI Platform As a Service updates	9
3.1 - Workload management system	9
Federated Cloud Environment	9
3.2 - PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning	12
Support for automatic deployment of the Workload Management System	12
PaaS components for provisioning - deployed components	14
PaaS components for provisioning - new components	16
3.3 - AI as a Service	18
3.4 - Advanced AI Tools: Distributed and Federated training	20
3.5 - Interactive developments tools	24
4. - Conclusion	25
References	26

LIST OF TABLES

- [Table 1: Components and actions: status and description](#)

LIST OF FIGURES

- [Figure 1: AI4EOSC platform](#)
- [Figure 2: AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project](#)
- [Figure 3: Consul WAN gossip architecture](#)
- [Figure 4: PaaS Orchestration and provisioning components](#)
- [Figure 5: AI platform customization via resource orchestration](#)
- [Figure 6: Aias a Service](#)
- [Figure 7: Index UI to access the cluster metrics](#)
- [Figure 8: Landing page of the cluster](#)
- [Figure 9: AI4EOSC Platform - Federated learning server](#)
- [Figure 10: Secrets management for the FL server from the dashboard](#)
- [Figure 11: General configuration for the federated learning server.
Docker tags: latest and tokens](#)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable outlines the status of the different components and functionalities operated within WP4 during the second part of the AI4EOSC project and aimed to be an integral part of the AI4EOSC second release (AI4EOSC 2nd Release). Both architecture and roadmap evolution are briefly discussed. From there, the definition of the activities aimed at completing the functionalities of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release are depicted.

Specifically, the architecture and roadmap update are detailed, including the status and description of the platform components and actions. Concerning the services updates, the following components are explained in detail: workload management system, PaaS orchestration and provisioning as the new features like the new monitoring service and the Federation service PaaS microservice.

Other updates consist of the AI as a service system, the advanced tools for AI including federated learning, distributed learning and incremental learning, and finally the introduction of the CVAT tool for image labeling.

1. - INTRODUCTION

During the second year of the AI4EOSC project, activities have been continued to improve components and functionalities of the AI4EOSC platform to be provided to the final users. Initially collected and described in the deliverable D4.1 [[AI4EOSC-D4.1](#)], in the deliverable D4.2 [[AI4EOSC-D4.2](#)] it is described the work carried out on each of them, as well as the deviations from the initially defined plan.

The present deliverable reports a status update of the services and tools that will be part of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The document is structured as follows.

In [Section 2](#), the update related to the architecture and roadmap evaluation is given, together with a summary of the current status of each component and actions.

In [Section 3](#), the status of the different components as well as the status of the AI PaaS is deeply reported, including the development implemented for the different services.

In [Section 4](#) the conclusions are drawn.

2. - PROGRESS REPORT

2.1 - ARCHITECTURE UPDATES

This section provides an overview of the architectural updates of the related components developed by WP4. In particular the present deliverable will address updates related to the following macro components (see [Figure 1](#) for details):

- PaaS orchestration and provisioning,
- AI as a Service,
- AI4EOSC platform related components.

[System Context] AI4EOSC Platform
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 1: AI4EOSC platform²

² Original figure: https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#ai4eosc_view

2.2 - ROADMAP EVALUATION UPDATE

This section evaluates how the roadmap stated in the Deliverable D4.1 has been realized so far, specifying when changes from the initial plan have occurred. To do so, [Table 1](#) shows the different components and actions planned for the AI4EOSC 2nd Release and their status and description. In order to detail the level of compliance or implementation of the different actions or components, in [Table 1](#) the green bullet (●) represents that the component is ready, the blue bullet (●) that it is under testing phase, and the orange one (●) that it is under development or is a prototype.

Table 1: Components and actions: status and description. Green bullet: component ready; blue bullet: component under testing; orange bullet: component under development or prototype.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Federated Service Catalogue/ design and implementation	● The service has been designed and the first prototype has been implemented and is under evaluation. It will be launched in the second release.
PaaS Monitoring and Metering/design and implementation	● The service has been designed and a prototype has been implemented. It will be released in the next release.
PaaS Orchestrator/Nomad deployment	● The automatic deployment of Nomad + Consul has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator. Minor fixes have been implemented.
PaaS Orchestrator/OSCAR deployment	● The automatic deployment of OSCAR on top of Kubernetes has been designed and implemented in the PaaS Orchestrator. MinIO object storage service has been also implemented in the related environment. Minor fixes have been implemented.
PaaS Orchestrator/Federated Catalogue integration	● The service is on its prototypical version. The information to be integrated in the Federated Catalogue has been defined and the initial version of the catalogue has been populated. It will be released in the next release.
Cloud Provider Ranker/algorithm update	● The datasource have been identified and the related dataset has been defined. A number of AI-based algorithms have been selected and are under evaluation. It will be released in the next release.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Infrastructure Manager automation + OSCAR integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OSCAR components automation has been implemented via the IM. The IM can deploy OSCAR services defined in TOSCA templates.
OSCAR manager/Reduced cold start	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To mitigate cold start, a method for prefetching Docker images in the Kubernetes nodes when creating an OSCAR service has been implemented.
OSCAR Manager/Interfaces + Libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The following features have been integrated in OSCAR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of services that expose their own API as an OSCAR service. • Initial multitenancy support.
Workload Management System implementation and automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nomad and Consul infrastructures have been deployed and Traefik has been used as load balancer.
Interactive Development environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VScode and JupyterLab have been integrated as the two available interactive development environments (IDEs) and can be used throughout the platform.
CVAT integration for image labelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CVAT is integrated as an open-source tool for image and video annotation provided as a cloud or self-hosted application.

3. - AI PLATFORM AS A SERVICE UPDATES

In the present section we report an overview of the improvements carried out about technologies and solutions chosen for each of the components. In addition, in [Figure 2](#) the architecture of the platform together with its components and their relations is presented, highlighting the WP4 tasks involved.

Figure 2: AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project

3.1 - WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Federated Cloud Environment

The Consul deployment strategy will be updated from the description in D4.2. Previously the deployment was following a LAN federation strategy, in which each node needed to have connectivity with nodes placed in different datacenters. However, clients of different sites are connected to different private subnets, so this need was not being met.

In this new deployment strategy, Consul [[Consul](#)] servers connect with each other following a **WAN approach**. This means that Consul clients only communicate with the Consul servers of their own datacenter (LAN), and these servers are responsible for communicating the datacenters with each other. This new strategy avoids temporal disconnection of some clients that used to happen when following strict LAN strategy.

Figure 3: Consul WAN gossip architecture

This deployment approach gives the possibility of enabling a Consul service called “mesh gateways” that serves as a proxy between Consul datacenters. With this service, all the communications between servers of different data centers are carried using a single public IP for each site, which allows deploying multiple servers for redundancy purposes without the necessity of assigning one IP for each consul server.

The Nomad vision of the different nodes will not change with this Consul update.

In addition, we plan to improve the handling of the Raft consensus protocol. This task is critical because losing the connectivity with one datacenter can break the entire Raft consensus protocol. To address this, we plan to automate the process of making backups of Raft state, thus making the recovery process easier.

Finally, we plan to improve the Consul [[Consul](#)] and Nomad [[Nomad](#)] token management when running the Ansible [[Ansible](#)] roles, avoiding the use of placeholders on the Ansible configuration templates. At present, in fact, the Consul and Nomad configuration start before the token is created. To overcome

such limitations, a token placeholder has been used. In this way, the token placeholder is replaced as soon as the real token is generated. However this led to a failure of the Molecule [\[AnsibleMolecule\]](#) idempotency test. Work is going on to solve this issue.

Nomad supports different storage plugins, which allow scheduling tasks with externally created storage volumes. Storage plugins are third-party plugins that conform to the Container Storage Interface (CSI) [\[CSI-Specification\]](#) specification.

Storage plugins are created dynamically as Nomad jobs, unlike device and task driver plugins that need to be installed and configured on each client. Nomad tracks which clients have instances of a given plugin, and communicates with plugins over a Unix domain socket that it creates inside the plugin's tasks. A list of available CSI plugins can be found in the Kubernetes CSI documentation [\[Kubernetes-CSI\]](#).

There are three **types** of CSI plugins. **Controller Plugins** communicate with the storage provider's APIs. For example, for a job that needs an AWS EBS volume, Nomad will tell the controller plugin that it needs a volume to be "published" to the client node, and the controller will make the API calls to AWS to attach the EBS volume to the right EC2 instance. **Node Plugins** do the work on each client node, like creating mount points. **Monolith Plugins** are plugins that perform both the controller and node roles in the same instance. Not every plugin provider has or needs a controller; that's specific to the provider implementation.

In addition to the previous points, some minor Nomad improvements will be carried out:

- Update the Nomad configuration to avoid the removal of Docker images once the job that downloaded them is terminated. This will improve job deployment time.
- Add a new metadata field in Nomad clients that shows the ID of the commit of the Ansible repository that was used to build that client. This will provide an easy way for Nomad administrators to assess the cluster consistency.
- Develop a new Nomad task to download external datasets (eg. Zenodo) to Nextcloud when starting a job. More details on this task can be found in the section "External Integrations" in Deliverable D5.3.

3.2 - PAAS ORCHESTRATION AND PROVISIONING

The PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning functionalities are provided via a set of services whose description and interactions are depicted in [Figure 4](#). Looking towards the second AI4EOSC release (AI4EOSC 2nd Release), the following functionalities have been implemented and tested.

[Container] PaaS Orchestration and provisioning
Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 4: PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning components³

Support for automatic deployment of the Workload Management System

The automatic deployment of the core components of the Workload Management System, i.e. Nomad [Nomad] and Consul [Consul], have been implemented by means of a TOSCA [TOSCA] template and Ansible Roles, developed by CSIC and UPV. The TOSCA template provides a standardised

³ Original figure: https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#orchestration_container_view

blueprint for the deployment of Nomad and Consul, while the Ansible roles automate the configuration of the infrastructure provisioned through the Infrastructure Manager [IM]. This ensures that the deployment process is fast, reliable, and repeatable, reducing the risk of errors and minimising the time and effort required for manual deployment.

The TOSCA template for the Nomad cluster deployment created in the first release has been improved, moving all the configuration tasks to a unified Ansible role that can be used either to configure a new site to the production platform, or to deploy new virtual clusters. Thus, only managing a set of Ansible roles improves the reproducibility of having a similar cluster either using physical or virtual clusters. Furthermore, a set of molecule tests [AnsibleMolecule] has been added to ensure the correct functionality of the Ansible roles and to improve the quality of the code.

A new TOSCA template is under testing to enable the deployment of a cluster that will join an already existing one to merge the amount of resources of both clusters.

The above mentioned TOSCA templates have been modified, tested and promoted to production to be used with the PaaS orchestrator

Production TOSCA templates

Nomad+Consul, Latest release (IM):

https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc.yaml

Nomad+Consul, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator):

<https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/nomad.yaml>

OSCAR, Latest release (IM):

<https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/oscar.yaml>

OSCAR, Latest release (PaaS Orchestrator):

<https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc/tosca-templates/-/blob/master/oscar.yaml>

Testing TOSCA templates

Nomad+Consul merging existing cluster (IM):

https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/main/templates/nomad_ai4eosc_join.yaml

PaaS components for provisioning - deployed components

PaaS AAI mechanism

The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS components layer is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service [[INDIGO-IAM](#)] (INDIGO-IAM) that leverages the OpenID Connect and OAuth2.0 [[OIDC](#), [OAuth2.0](#)] protocols.

- No major updates made to this bug fixing release.

Latest release (v1.9.0): <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam/releases/tag/v1.9.0>

Infrastructure Manager (IM)

An open-source framework designed to simplify the access and usability of IaaS clouds. It automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring and update of virtualized infrastructures.

- No major updates made to this bug fixing release.

Latest release (v1.16.0): <https://github.com/grycap/im/releases/tag/v1.16.0>

PaaS Orchestrator

Built with Java technologies and on the open-source workflow manager “Flowable” [[Flowable](#)], the Orchestrator allows federating heterogeneous resource providers and orchestrate the deployment of TOSCA templates, selecting the best provider according to criteria like the data location, the Service Level Agreement (SLA) and monitoring information. It provides a set of APIs to create, monitor and manage the deployments.

The Orchestrator has been updated with the following improvements.

- The possibility to manage the creation/deletion of IAM clients via Orchestrator. The INDIGO-IAM [[INDIGO-IAM](#)] client resource is completely managed by the Orchestrator: when a user submits the request of creation of a deployment requiring an INDIGO-IAM client, the Orchestrator creates the client, and when the user triggers the deletion of the deployment the Orchestrator deletes the corresponding INDIGO-IAM client;
- Added a parameter to force the deletion of a deployment. This may not delete some resources, for example IAM clients;

- Added a group authorization. Now the check is directly performed by the Orchestrator that stops the user's request when the used group is not allowed for the user;
- Added skipping monitoring workflow when the monitoring url is not specified;
- Metadata has been enriched with the information of preferred_username contained in the user's token;

Last release (v.2.8.0): <https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator/releases/tag/v2.8.0-FINAL>

PaaS Dashboard

It's a Flask [[Flask](#)] application with a SQL database (MySQL) that enables users to interact easily with the services of the PaaS, particularly the Orchestrator, to create TOSCA-based deployments. The dashboard provides a user-friendly interface for managing and monitoring deployments (see [Figure 5](#) for more details).

- No major updates made to this bug fixing release.

Latest release (v3.2.1): <https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator-dashboard/releases/tag/v3.2.1>

Figure 5: AI platform customization via resource orchestration

PaaS components for provisioning - new components

As already mentioned in D4.2, the following services and tools have not been included in the first AI4EOSC release due to the fact that they are under development and will be included in the second release.

Hereafter is presented the status of those components that will be part of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

Federation Registry

Efforts have been made to replace the Service Level Agreement Tool (SLAT) [SLAT] and the Configuration Management Database (CMDB) [CMDB] for several reasons, in particular because they are outdated tools with vulnerabilities. Thus, two tools have been developed: the Federation Registry [FederationRegistry], that is a Python web application providing public REST API to inspect the configurations of the federated providers, and the Federation Registry Feeder [FederationRegistryFeeder], that is a Python script used to populate the Federation Registry. The PaaS Orchestrator has been adapted to integrate these tools. We defined a roadmap that foresees the following steps:

- Creation of the Data Type Objects (DTO) that defines the entities required by the Federation Registry (especially those returned by the API that the Orchestrator will contact);

- Creation of functions that map the entities returned from the federation registry to what the Orchestrator expects and that will be used in the other steps of the workflow.

Latest release:

- Federation Registry (v.1.0.0-alpha.5) - <https://github.com/infndatacloud/federation-registry/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha.5>
- Federation Registry Feeder (v1.0.0-alpha)- <https://github.com/infndatacloud/federation-registry-feeder/releases/tag/v1.0.0-alpha>

Monitoring and Ranking system with integrated AI

In the default configuration, the PaaS-Orchestrator determines the provider to which the deployment creation request is submitted based on an ordered list of providers, selected according to the group the user belongs to. This list is provided by the Cloud Provider Ranker [CPR] service, which applies a ranking algorithm using a limited set of metrics related to deployments and the Service Level Agreements defined for the providers. The INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator submits the deployment to the first provider on the list, and in case of failure, it moves to the next provider until the list is exhausted.

The new AI-based orchestrator⁴ approach is an evolution of the actual ranking system, aimed to improve it and optimize resource usage adopting Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques.

In this context, significant preparatory work was carried out to identify the most relevant metrics, as well as the sources from which these metrics can be obtained. The main sources we identified are: Orchestrator logs, Orchestrator Dashboard DB, and monitoring service. The subsequent preparation of the dataset allowed us to study the use case and to identify and compare various AI techniques. The proposed approach involves the creation of two models: a predictive model for the classification of deployment success/failure and a regression model for the deployment creation time. A linear combination of the outputs of the two models, together with training on recent and moving time windows, allows for the definition of an ordered list of providers that the orchestrator can use for submitting deployments.

Then we started to work for the automatization of metrics collection, using Kafka as main technology. To reduce the number of sources to contact, we moved the useful information stored in the Orchestrator Dashboard DB directly into the

⁴ AI-based orchestrator: <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/AI-based+orchestrator>

Orchestrator logs. This work will allow us to get a dataset for AI purposes just contacting Kafka.

The components are tested in a cloud pre-production environment.

3.3 - AI AS A SERVICE

In AI4EOSC the open-source OSCAR [OSCAR] platform is used to offer AI models as a service, enabling quick deployment and scaling of AI models and providing an accessible and efficient means to perform inference (see [Figure 6](#) for links and interaction of AI as a Service components with the other software stacks).

[System Context] AI as a Service
Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 6: AI as a Service⁵

The most recent functionalities improvements and implementations in this component are the following.

- **Accounting:** A Prometheus [Prometheus] instance has been deployed to monitor the usage of the OSCAR cluster in terms of resources consumed by inference executions. Through the Kubernetes agent kube-state-

⁵ Original image: https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#aiaas_view

metrics⁶, metrics are extracted from each K8S resource and stored on the time series database of Prometheus, so then the information can be retrieved by simple SQL queries when needed. On the other hand, more specific metrics about users and deployed services are collected by means of the GoAccess tool [GoAccess], which uses web logs to get information about web traffic. With this tool, metrics such as the number of deployed services over a period of time or the geolocation of the users interacting with the cluster are gathered. These metrics, accessed via an index UI (see [Figure 7](#) for details), are of special interest for the use cases of the project (WP6) and also external use cases of the platform, like the ones coming from the iMagine project [iMagine]. In addition, a landing page has been created at <https://oscar-metrics.grycap.net/oscar-ai4eosc/> to provide easy access to the compiled metrics.

Figure 7. Index UI to access the cluster metrics

- **Multitenancy enhancement:** As reported in D4.2, to isolate the services and MinIO buckets between users that make use of the cluster, a mechanism to support multitenancy was implemented in OSCAR. To improve this functionality, we increased control over the services that users create so that only the service owner can make changes or delete them.
- **Updating module:** A method of synchronizing the models in the AI4EOSC dashboard and the OSCAR cluster automatically has been implemented. It uses the Jenkins pipeline to update the models deployed as services on the cluster when these models are changed.
- **Authentication on exposed services:** Applications that use OSCAR exposed services [[OSCAR_ES](#)] may not have a native authentication

⁶ Kubernetes agent kube-state-metrics, <https://github.com/kubernetes/kube-state-metrics/tree/main>

method. These services can expose not only an API but also other types of resources, such as a UI, in the case of Jupyter Notebooks. Therefore, since it would be resource-consuming and a potential security risk if someone had unrestricted access to it, authentication via Ingress has been enabled to better secure access.

- **Securing images:** A mechanism to restrict the origin of the Docker images has been implemented to avoid the deployment of malicious Docker images in the OSCAR cluster deployed for the project at <https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>. This way, only images from the AI4EOSC Docker image repository can be used to deploy OSCAR services.
- **OSCAR generic script:** To easily integrate the creation of an AI application as a service, a generic script for inference has been implemented, thus allowing any DEEPaaS API-compliant model to be deployed effectively, abstracting the complexities of code implementation from the users.

As previously mentioned, we have deployed an OSCAR cluster to use for inference executions on the project. [Figure 8](#) shows the customized login of the cluster's landing page at <https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>.

Figure 8: Landing page of the cluster

3.4 - ADVANCED AI TOOLS: DISTRIBUTED AND FEDERATED TRAINING

Task 4.4 aims to support users in the development of advanced techniques for training AI models (ML/DL). In particular, as developed in D4.2, further work on privacy preserving machine learning (PPML) by means of the implementation of a federated learning (FL) server has been done (see [Figure 9](#)). The FL server allows users to perform federated learning training in a simple and intuitive way by deploying the server from the dashboard.

[Component] AI4EOSC Platform - Federated learning server

Tuesday, June 4, 2024 at 10:11 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 9: AI4EOSC Platform - Federated learning server⁷

Several improvements have been made to the federated server since D4.2, both from the point of view of privacy and security and regarding usability:

- Client authentication.** In the classic federated server implementation, clients can connect to the server to start the training given the endpoint on which it is deployed. However, this can be a challenge if attackers try to join the training to perform a model poisoning attack, as they only need to know the model being trained and the endpoint of the server. In this sense, a secret management system has been implemented so that, given a deployment of the federated server, as many tokens as necessary can be created. The server will then be in charge of distributing the corresponding secret/token to each client, who will need to enter it when connecting in order to join the training. The secret management system allows to revoke secrets (e.g. in case a client is removed from the system), as well as to create new ones [\[Sáinz-Pardo Díaz et al.\]](#).

This secret management system has been created using Vault [\[Vault\]](#), and the management of secrets can be done from the Vault IDE or in a friendly way from the dashboard itself, once the server is deployed (see [Figure 10](#)).

⁷ Original image: https://structurizr.com/workspace/73873/diagrams#fl_component_view

Figure 10: Secrets management for the FL server from the dashboard.

In order to integrate the client authentication system with Flower [Flower], we have implemented some extensions to the Flower library to work alongside Vault, that are included in the server and client sides. Specifically, it can be found in [ai4os/ai4-flwr], branch *tokens*. In addition, we have developed some modifications to the Flower library to manage the credentials that allow to enable or disable the connection of each client according to the token introduced (see [AI4EOSC/flower], branch *credentials*). For more information on how to use the federated learning server including the secrets/tokens for client authentication, check the official project documentation [AI4OSdocs]. Different video tutorials are provided to users both including the secret management⁸ and without it⁹.

When creating the federated server, the user can choose whether to include the possibility of authenticating clients with tokens, or not to use this functionality. In the first case the docker tag *tokens* must be selected in the general configuration, while in the second case the docker tag *latest* must be used (see Figure 11).

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v7blpOB92C8>

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FrgVummLNbU&t=42s>

Configure training: **Federated learning server**

Marketplace / Federated learning server / Train Show help

1 General configuration 2 Hardware configuration 3 Federated configuration

Deployment options

Deployment title* Deployment description

Service to run

Fedserver Jupyter Vscode

Custom domain

Docker options

Docker image

Docker tag

- latest
- latest
- tokens

Figure 11: General configuration for the federated learning server. Docker tags: latest and tokens.

- Including new aggregation strategies and enhancing the current ones.** Some implemented aggregation functions such as *FedProx* require additional parameters that can be customized (e.g. μ in the case of *FedProx*). This has been updated so that if a user deploys a federated server with this strategy, they can customize this parameter from the dashboard. In addition, new aggregation functions have been included, such as *Federated Average with Momentum* (which also includes parameters that the user can customize from the dashboard when selecting it) and *Federated Median*. Note that further work is in progress concerning the development and testing of new aggregations strategies to be included within the Flower framework and also within the federated server deployed in AI4EOSC.

Regarding the implementation of FL in AI4EOSC, the following paper has been published and presented at the *12th ACM Workshop on Information Hiding and Multimedia Security* [[Sáinz-Pardo Díaz et al.](#)].

Furthermore, in order to provide users with a more complete set of tools in this scope, the integration of the federated learning framework NVFlare (powered by NVIDIA) [[NVFlare](#)] is being analyzed in the same way as it has been done with Flower. This is currently being tested prior to integrating it into the platform.

In addition, concerning distributed machine learning (DML), while with federated learning we are covering the privacy-aware distributed learning approach, we have also focused on the computing-resources-aware distributed learning one. Specifically, the objective is to allow users to perform ML/DL training on multiple deployments, or on a single deployment with multiple GPUs. In particular, the

data parallelism method is adopted, i.e. the data is artificially distributed to train the model on multiple workers. Thus, data is distributed across multiple nodes in the computing environment.

First of all, if the data is already distributed naturally on multiple machines (on the AI4EOSC platform, on local computers or on external cloud providers), it is sufficient to use the federated learning server. Thus, a client will be created on each node where the data is distributed and the DML training will be performed using Flower and the FL architecture proposed in D4.2.

On the other hand, in the case where we have a single deployment with multiple GPUs, and all the data is on that single deployment, users may be interested in distributing the training among all the available GPUs. In this sense, this can be done using Horovod [[Horovod](#)], and a template for doing this using Tensorflow [[Tensorflow](#)] has been included in the AI4OS documentation together with some hints and guides [[DL_AI4OSdocs](#)].

Furthermore, also in the AI4OS documentation section concerning advanced AI tools, some guides on the use of Incremental (online) Learning have been included [[IL_AI4OSdocs](#)].

3.5 - INTERACTIVE DEVELOPMENTS TOOLS

Several adjustments and improvements have been made to the IDE repository and its CI/CD pipeline; e.g., relocation from deephdc/deep-oc-generic-dev to ai4os/ai4os-dev-env and transition from JePLv1 to a native Jenkinsfile, streamlining the build process. Old versions of the Docker images have been replaced with TensorFlow 2.14 and CUDA images from NVIDIA, and the INFO.md file along with VSCode plugins are now dynamically loaded from GitHub during the container build via the deep-start script. Another enhancement has been made to the cookiecutter templates by simplifying the a4-template-adv, reducing user input fields, and improving input field explanations.

Plans for the near future involve removing "-cpu" and "-gpu" tags for TensorFlow-based images, as the "gpu" images appear in on-going evaluation to function well on CPU-only systems since TensorFlow 2.0. There is also consideration of moving from setup.py and setup.cfg to pyproject.toml for the a4-template, in line with modern Python packaging practices. These updates aim to enhance usability and streamline the development environment.

CVAT for image labeling

The Computer Vision Annotation Tools (CVAT) [[CVAT](#)] is an open-source tool for image and video annotation provided as a cloud or self-hosted application. It supports various image formats (backed by Pillow [[pillow](#)]) and video formats (backed by ffmpeg [[ffmpeg](#)]), as well as 3D data. CVAT offers a wide range of

annotation tools enabling annotation of different shapes such as rectangles, polygons, polylines, skeletons or tagging and attribute annotation tools. CVAT has semi-automated and automated labelling features: interactors (e.g., Segment Anything Model), detectors (e.g., YOLO v3), trackers (e.g. TransT - Transformer Tracking).

Within the AI4EOSC context, CVAT will be forked from its original repository and adjusted to make it deployable in the Nomad (see Deliverable D5.3 -WP5 Updated implementation plan and WP5 progress report [[AI4EOSC-D5.3](#)] for more details). The modifications include:

- Adding the ability to *specify custom ports* for different CVAT services (e.g., Identity and Access Management, Open Policy Agent, Postgres and in-memory Redis databases) in order to ensure visibility of the services and proper functionality of the annotation tool.
- Adding a *superuser creation command*, which takes into account repeated deployment occurring within Nomad.
- Adjusting the original Docker image to enable *mounting of the AI4EOSC storage* [[ai4-storage](#)] with rclone [[rclone](#)]. The storage serves as both the annotation data source and persistence enabler between the application shutdowns.

4. - CONCLUSION

The present document is a demonstrator of the progress made within the AI4EOSC project, in particular between the first version of the AI4EOSC platform (AI4EOSC 1st Release) and the second version (AI4EOSC 2nd Release).

In particular, the update related to the architecture and roadmap evaluation has been presented in [Section 2](#), supported by a graphical representation of the status of each component.

In [Section 3](#), instead, the status of the main components of the platform have been reported together with the activity carried out and the main developments that will be part of the final release.

In general, the activities are proceeding smoothly to have all the components ready and the related functionality fully available for the next release of AI4EOSC.

REFERENCES

[AI4EOSC-D4.1] Marica Antonacci, Álvaro López, Aida Palacio, Ignacio Heredia, Judith Sainz-Pardo, Jaime Céspedes, Germán Moltó, Amanda Calatrava, Miguel Caballer, Viet Tran, Martin Seleng, Stefan Dlugolinsky, Mario David, Daniel San Martín, & Lisana Berberi. (2023). D4.1 - Implementation plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7649073>

[AI4EOSC-D4.2] Constantini, A., Donvito, G., Sainz-Pardo, J., Kozlov, V., Tran, V., Dlugolinsky, S., Šeleng, M., & Alarcón, C. (2024). D4.2 - First release of the AI Platform as a Service. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869931>.

[AI4EOSC-D5.3] Deliverable D5.3 [10.5281/zenodo.11485132](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485132)

[AI4EOSC/flower] AI4EOSC/flower GitHub repository: modifications to the Flower library to manage the credentials. <https://github.com/AI4EOSC/flower/tree/credentials>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[ai4os/ai4-flwr] ai4os/ai4-flwr GitHub repository: extensions to the Flower library. <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-flwr/tree/tokens>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[AI4OSdocs] AI4OS docs. How-to: use a tool. Federated server including client authentication. <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/tools/federated-server.html#federated-learning-training-in-ai4eosc>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[ai4-storage] AI4EOSC Nextcloud storage: <https://share.services.ai4os.eu>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Ansible] Ansible, <https://ansible.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

[AnsibleMolecule] Ansible Molecule, <https://ansible.readthedocs.io/projects/molecule/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[CMDB] Change management database, <https://github.com/indigo-dc/cmdb>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[CPR] Cloud Provider Rancker, <https://github.com/indigo-dc/CloudProviderRanker>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Consul] Consul, <https://www.consul.io/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[CSI-Specification] Container Storage Interface, <https://github.com/container-storage-interface/spec>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

[CVAT] Computer Vision Annotation Tool: <https://www.cvat.ai/>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

[DL_AI4OSdocs] Distributed learning, AI4OS docs. <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/distributed-learning.html>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[FederationRegistryFeeder] Federation Registry Feeder, <https://github.com/infndatacloud/federation-registry-feeder>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[FederationRegistry] Federation Registry is a web application, <https://github.com/infndatacloud/federation-registry>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[ffmpeg] FFmpeg: <https://ffmpeg.org/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Flask] Flask, <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/2.2.x/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Flowable] Flowable, <https://www.flowable.com/open-source>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Flower] Flower, <https://flower.ai/>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

[GoAccess] GoAccess visual web log analyzer. <https://goaccess.io/> Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Horovod] Horovod, <https://horovod.ai/>. Accessed: 16/08/2024.

[IL_AI4OSdocs] Incremental learning, AI4OS docs. <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/incremental-learning.html>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[IM] Infrastructure Manager, <https://www.grycap.upv.es/im>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[iImagine] iImagine project, <https://zenodo.org/records/11520846>, Accessed: 08/08/2024

[INDIGO-IAM] INDIGO-IAM service, <https://github.com/indigo-iam/iam>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[Kubernetes-CSI] Kubernetes CSI Developer Documentation - Drivers. <https://kubernetes-csi.github.io/docs/drivers.html>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

[Nomad] Nomad, <https://www.nomadproject.io/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[NVFlare] NVFlare: NVIDIA Federated Learning Application Runtime Environment. <https://github.com/NVIDIA/NVFlare>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[OAuth2.0] Oauth 2.0, <https://oauth.net/2/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024

[OIDC] OpenID Connect, <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[OSCAR] OSCAR, <https://oscar.grycap.net>. Accessed: 08/08/2024

[OSCAR_ES] OSCAR Exposed Services. <https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/exposed-services/>. Accessed: 08/08/2024

[Pillow] Pillow: <https://pillow.readthedocs.io>. Accessed: 08/08/2024

[Prometheus] Prometheus metering and alerting. <https://prometheus.io/> . Accessed: 08/08/2024

[**rclone**] RCLONE: <https://rclone.org/> . Accessed: 08/08/2024

[**Sáinz-Pardo Díaz et al.**] Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, J., Heredia Canales, A., Heredia Cachá, I., Tran, V., Nguyen, G., Alibabaei, K., Obregón Ruiz, M., Rebolledo Ruiz, S., & López García, Á. Making Federated Learning Accessible to Scientists: The AI4EOSC Approach. In Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Workshop on Information Hiding and Multimedia Security (IH&MMSec '24). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 253–264. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3658664.3659642> .

[**TOSCA**] TOSCA OASIS Standard, https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=tosca. Accessed: 08/08/2024.

[**Tensorflow**] Abadi, M., & TensorFlow, A. A. B. P. (2016, November). Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous distributed systems. In *Proceedings of the 12th USENIX symposium on operating systems design and implementation (OSDI'16)(Savannah, GA, USA)* (pp. 265-283).

[**Vault**] Vault, <https://www.vaultproject.io/>. Accessed: 12/08/2024.

